

1.1 Lean Mindset [categorized under Principle 1: Embrace change to deliver customer value]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods and takes organizational measures for systematically reducing waste.

Examples for investigated aspects: Lightweight methodologies, discarded low-value activities, discarded low-value artifacts

1.2 Change Orientation [categorized under Principle 1: Embrace change to deliver customer value]

Goal of the assessment: The organization encourages a change embracing mindset, use proper methods, techniques and tools for identifying and implementing change.

Examples for investigated aspects: New processes, new roles, new tools to support change

1.3 Iterative & Incremental Value Delivery [categorized under Principle 1: Embrace change to deliver customer value]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for generating value in small cycles at a defined cadence.

Examples for investigated aspects: Sprint structure, Spikes

1.4 Flexibility in Value Delivery [categorized under Principle 1: Embrace change to deliver customer value]

Goal of the assessment: The organization shows a clear attitude towards a flexible decision-making process for customer value creation.

Examples for investigated aspects: Delayed critical decisions, No upfront design

2.1 Value Delivery Planning [categorized under Principle 2: Plan and deliver software frequently]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for planning the delivery of value by means of realized user stories, epics or features.

Examples for investigated aspects: Release planning, Work package estimation, Collaborative planning, Backlog management, User stories

2.2 Value Delivery Actualization [categorized under Principle 2: Plan and deliver software frequently]

Goal of the assessment: The organization is capable of using proper methods, techniques and tools for delivering Software (features) frequently and at the demanded pace.

Examples for investigated aspects: DevOps practices (e.g., pipeline automation, modularization, feature toggles, A/B testing), reduced cycle times

3.1 Psychological Safety [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization intentionally strives for ensuring the mental well-being of its people.

Examples for investigated aspects: No overtime, No unpaid overtime, Voluntary overtime, Sustainable workload

3.2 Effective Communication [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization provides open and transparent dialogue infrastructures for its people.

Examples for investigated aspects: Informal oral communication, Face-to-face communication, Physical/Digital Kaffeeküche meetings, Constructive criticism

3.3 Unit Empowerment [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for encouraging its units towards value creation and increasing their engagement.

Examples for investigated aspects: Motivated unit members, high engagement in work activities, high engagement in voluntary activities, positive responses from the unit on employee surveys

3.4 Unit Collaboration [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for enabling collective value creation within and among its units.

Examples for investigated aspects: Co-creation, Social get togethers, PI-planning (or similar)

3.5 Unit Autonomy [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for enabling self-organization and decentralized decision making among its units.

Examples for investigated aspects: Teams select their leaders, Teams without leaders, decentral decision-making, feature teams, contextually appropriate organizational formations

3.6 Personal Growth [categorized under Principle 3: Human centric]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for facilitating both technical and social learning activities, prioritizing its members' individual growth.

Examples for investigated aspects: Technical trainings, Non-technical trainings, coaching initiatives, defined learning paths

4.1 Testing [categorized under Principle 4: Technical Excellence]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for testing and is it organized in a way that errors are systematically found before deploying the software.

Examples for investigated aspects: Unit testing and Mocking frameworks, Test automation on integration and system level, Test Driven Development, Behavioral design based testing.

4.2 Continuous Improvement [categorized under Principle 4: Technical Excellence]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for employing continuous improvement in throughout the entire software lifecycle.

Examples for investigated aspects: PDSA/PDCA Cycle, Cost-benefit analysis, Established feedback loops

4.3 Design and Coding Practices [categorized under Principle 4: Technical Excellence]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques and tools for first establishing, and then ensuring the usage of established design and coding practices in the software development process

Examples for investigated aspects: Pair programming, refactoring, Code- and Design Inspections, Design and Architectural Analysis, static analysis, dynamic analysis, technical debt assessment, coding best practices, design best practices.

4.4 Data-driven Development and Operation [categorized under Principle 4: Technical Excellence]

Goal of the assessment: The organization uses proper methods, techniques, tools and data for identifying and measuring core aspects of development and operation.

Examples for investigated aspects: Software Quality Dashboards, DevOps KPIs, Application Monitoring

5.1 Customer Involvement [categorized under Principle 5: Customer Collaboration]

Goal of the assessment: The organization systematically involves the customers in the product development process.

Examples for investigated aspects: Prototyping, On-site customer (Product Owner)

5.2 Customer Decision Making [categorized under Principle 5: Customer Collaboration]

Goal of the assessment: The organization systematically tries to empower the customer to take an active role in the customer value related decisions.

Examples for investigated aspects: Customer Acceptance Test, Feature Planning, Prioritization based on customer value, Customer value related KPIs